

ФИЛОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

Kamala BAYRAMOVA

PhD student, Azerbaijan University

Senior lecturer, Guba branch of ASPU, Azerbaijan

mrs.bayramova.kemale@gmail.com

ORCID iD:0000-0002-2233-0399

SOVIET TRUTHS IN SULEYMAN VALIYEV'S WORKS

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Abstract: Suleyman Valiyev came to literature in the 30s of the 20th century, considered one of the "bloodiest" years of Azerbaijan's history. During those years, he also wrote works promoting the Soviet regime by the requirements of the time. Hamid Sultanov, one of Azerbaijan's founders of the Soviet government, is presented as a positive hero in the story "Bigli Agha (Mr Moustached)", which he wrote on the subject of the revolution. Although, at first glance, it seems as if he was rooted in the requirements of the time in every period of his work, in reality, the writer also showed the regime's true face.

The writer, who voluntarily went to the front during World War II, was wounded in the head in 1942 and captured by the fascists. The writer, who was investigated by the regime and sent into exile for being caught, described the realities he lived in his works after that time. In the novel "Knots", the writer sheds light on the fate of unjustly deported people by the Soviet system. In the memoir "How I Lived", the state's attitude to the people who gave their lives in the war is reflected in subtle strokes. Since the 1980s, Suleyman Valiyev, using the presence of "softening" in the field of literature, touches on the subject of bloody "reforms" and repressions carried out by the Soviet system. He reflects on the truths of repression in the essay "Chamanzaminli", the memoir "Shushabandli Azernashr", and the autobiographical novel "A bird with a broken wing has flown".

Suleyman Valiyev touched on the subject of Soviet realities more clearly and boldly in his memoirs written during the years of independence. In his unpublished series of biographies called "Unopened Pages", the writer clarified many issues that were forbidden to be written about during the Soviet years.

Keywords: Suleyman Valiyev, Soviet regime, repression, exile, captivity, autobiography

Introduction: The Soviet era of Azerbaijani literature is studied as a separate phase. The 20s of the 20th century are characterised as the fall of the Azerbaijan Republic, the beginning of the most terrible days of our history. The wave of repression started in 1917 and became massive in the 20s, reaching its peak in 1937 under the leadership of I. Stalin. As in all the countries that "joined" the Soviet empire, this influence left deep traces and opened irreparable wounds in the life of the Azerbaijani people. "The most difficult years of the last century" (1, p. 20) by sacrificing the writers, poets, and literary critics, who had the power to take our literature to the heights with their talent and ability, dealt a significant blow to both literature and the intellectual potential of our people, as well as the rich genetic heritage: "70-80 thousand intellectuals of Azerbaijan - scientists, writers, artists, teachers, youth, clergymen, employees of the Soviet and party administration, soldiers - in a word, all thinking minds, owners of unusual thinking were destroyed at one end" (5, p. 6).

At this stage, "For the first time, the government is trying to control the literary process by making decisions and resolutions to develop literature. The destructive nature of the revolution quickly took over literature and art. It pushed them to propagate Bolshevism" (7, p. 169). Writers who oppose the regime's ideology and include "dubious" points in their works become victims of the wave of repression. Prominent figures of our literary history such as H.Javid, Y.V.Chamanzaminli, A.Javad, M.Mushfiq, S.Mumtaz, A.Abid, A.Nazim, H.Zeynalli, H.Sanlı, S.Huseyn and hundreds of talents like them cannot escape from the clutches of the regime.

Researchers from different aspects are

investigating the genesis of the period of repression. However, the realities of the period become the object of study in the works of fiction written during that period and later. Suleyman Valiyev, one of the figures who entered the literature during the period when the repression wave "followed the literature extremely carefully", is known in our literature as the author of autobiographical works. Writing autobiographical works is an artistic technique used by this writer to directly convey the realities of his life and the fate of the Azerbaijani people in Soviet slavery to future generations. Suleyman Valiyev presented a part of his life and the lives of people he knew closely in his works; in fact, "he reflected the life history of a national man for more than half a century in his artistic works". (19, p. 25)

However, the writer had to comply with the requirements of this time regime. Sometimes, he wrote down the events that he wanted to turn into the subject of artistic thought, changing the concepts of space and history. Although Suleyman Valiyev's works were written by the requirements of the time, it would not be correct to consider him a "singer" of the Soviet era, to judge him without considering the period, environment, and requirements of the regime in which the author lived. The writer tried to draw attention to the regime's brutality in several works he wrote during the Soviet period. In the works he wrote during the years of "softening" in the field of literature, he gradually revealed the truths of the regime. If we systematise his creativity in terms of describing the realities of life, his works can be divided into three stages according to his period and ideology:

-1932-1945 years

- 1945-1980 years

- 1990-1996 years.

He was only sixteen when his first pen experience story, "The Savings Bank", was published in 1932. In his works written before the war period, the writer keeps up with the requirements of the time and presents the Soviet regime more reasonably than the previous structure. An example of this is the story "Bigly Agha (Mr Moustached)", which introduces Suleyman Valiyev to a wide readership in the field of literature. The work published in book form in 1937 is his first large-scale work. The story was written on the topic of revolution according to the demand of the time. Its main heroes are the participants of the revolution, who promoted the establishment of the Soviet regime. Characters such as Abbas Alijan (prototype of "Bigly Agha (Mr Moustached)" character) and Mustafa are prototypes of people whom the writer knows personally. In this work, the writer created the image of Hamid Sultanov, one of Azerbaijan's founders of the Soviet regime, and presented him as a positive hero. One of the writer's first works, the story "Moollah Mamish and the chest", is devoted to the exposure of mullahs and religious figures by the literary fashion of the time.

S. Valiyev's work has endeared him to a broad audience of readers - the story "Shor jullutu (Sandpiper)" tells about the miserable life of our compatriots living under the occupation of Tsarist Russia. By writing about the tragic fate of the hero named Ibish, the author created an artistic depiction of class inequality by showing the social conditions of the Azerbaijani people at that time and the difference between the life of the oil feudal lords and the ordinary people. The story describes how the people, entirely robbed by the tsarist government, had to fend for themselves to make a living. Issues such as the exploitation of the people's wealth by the oil feudal lords, the fact that the oil tycoons not only see a drop of oil to the ordinary people but even the residues that flow to the oil extraction fields are described based on actual events. Thirteen-year-old Ibish, the hero of the work, wants to catch one of the sandpipers floating in the oil-stained small lake to bring food to his sister, who is crying from hunger at home. At this time, the son of an oil feudal lord is mercilessly shot by Farrukh. "Shor jullutu (Sandpiper)" is one of the works that has won readers' love with its exciting and realistic theme and flowing style. The story has been translated into several languages and published many times. One of the highlights of the work is that in the introductory part, the writer compares the period of tsarist Russia with the Soviet period in his notes addressed to children and clearly shows his sympathy for the latter: "...Guys, you haven't seen those days. That's why you are happy: the children of that time were not cheerful and smiling like you. They did not have school education like you" (25, p. 7). In his works written before 1942, it is possible to find many sentences containing this type of sympathy for the Soviet system.

The writer who served in the military from 1937-1939, when the Great Patriotic War began, our great poet voluntarily joined the ranks of the army, refusing to accept Samad Vurgu's offer to stay in the rear and continue his activities. Even in the June 29, 1941 issue of "Literature" newspaper, together with writers like S. Valiyev, M. Jalal, and A. Valiyev, the

issue of loyalty and love for the state was reflected in the appeal addressed to the people to go to war. S. Valiyev fought heroically in the war, was known as Sila, continued his cooperation with newspapers here, and wrote propaganda and motivational articles. In 1942, when he was wounded in the head and captured by the fascists, the tragic period of the writer's life began. However, the war also caused the writer to be spiritually shaken, wake up, and see the truth. The realisation of truths, such as the fact that the Soviet state does not own its soldiers, pays for the mistakes of military officials with the lives of ordinary soldiers, and considers prisoners as traitors, becomes the beginning of S. Valiyev's spiritual awakening. On the one hand, the writer tries to confirm the loyalty of citizens, but on the other hand, he is disappointed by the attitude he sees in return. The writer, who had to keep up with the demands of the time, did not directly criticise the regime in his works after that time. In his works, he alludes to some issues implicitly and fictionalises some facts by changing the concepts of time and space. The writer later wrote this in his notes: "By the way, I want to reveal one of my creative secrets. In some "Arab stories", I wrote about the political struggles and clan and mafia gangs that were not allowed to be published at the time. I found solace in transferring such conflicts to another country. After all, silence is great oppression" (26, p. 24).

For example, looking at his story "The Fig Tree" is enough. The story tells about the hard life of Arabs. The colonialists wanted to eliminate the "disturbed Arab", their political enemy, by humiliating Mahmud as a human being. However, Mahmoud refuses to commit the crime after great hesitation. He cannot raise a hand to the friend of the people who is the enemy of the imperialists. If you look at Suleyman Valiyev's life, you can see that the story's subject parallels the real events he experienced. Suleyman Valiyev was the son of the people occupied by the Russian imperialists. The regime wanted to exile him from the country, threaten to stop the publication of his works, and involve him in the terrible plan against Samad Vurgun, the great poet of the people. If he helped, he would be "rewarded" by continuing his work in the Union of Writers and is provided with a new apartment; in short, "all doors would be open to him." But he does not become a participant in this insidious plan, regardless of the outcome.

Most of the works of the writer, who spent most of his life through wars, battles, and captivity, are in the autobiographical genre and on the theme of war. After all, "literature is a product of humanistic thought; it calls all humanistic people of the earth to condemn the war" (10, p. 26). Suleyman Valiyev, as a writer who personally experienced the pain of war and the fate of exile, remains faithful to this principle of literature.

In the novel "Controversial City", which is considered one of the best novels written on the subject of war, the horrors of that war, the human destinies that it left unfinished, the identity of the real saviours of the city of Trieste, the hypocritical policy of America and other issues are shed light on. The writer does not touch on the Soviet truths in this novel only because he dedicates it to the rules of discipline in the partisan units, the liberation of the city of Trieste, and the activities of the Soviet citizens in the movement. In this

novel, the author tries to prove that he is a loyal citizen of the Soviet state, explaining "why and how he survived" by highlighting his activities in the partisan movement. "... Even during the war, there were insulting rumours about the Transcaucasian national divisions destroyed in the battles of Kerch. "Controversial City" showed the participation of the soldiers of the Azerbaijani division captured in Kerch in the Resistance Movement and defended the honour of the soldiers of the 416th Azerbaijani division. Suleyman Valiyev himself was one of them" (9, p. 28). Through the autobiographical character Aslan, the writer presents the fate of captivity, the fascists' harsh and merciless treatment of prisoners, his escape from the camp, and his cooperation with partisan groups in the later stage of his struggle through the filter of artistic imagination.

He provides more detailed information about the fate of captivity, the events he lived and saw in the front in his memoir "From the Homeland," written in 1958, and the issues reflected in the novel "Controversial City". Here, the author conveys the events and facts to the reader, not in an artistic way but in a documentary, journalistic style. The writer, whom the fascists captured after being hit in the head, describes his escape from the prison camp, the help of the Italian girl who helped them in this case, his activities in partisan groups, his battles at the front, and his feelings when he returned to his homeland after the end of the war, down to the minor details. He completes the lot of the work by talking about his departure to return to Baku and his dreams about his native land. In his memoirs, Suleyman Valiyev touched on the issues of the Soviet state's neglect of former prisoners of war and lack of ownership in an episodic way and covert form. He describes the dire conditions on the ship where the prisoners were transported and the thirst and hunger they faced at the waiting stations. In the continuation of the work, the chief of the military mission of the Soviet government in the Near and Middle East countries, under the leadership of Anisim Karasov, talks about the richness of the feast organised in connection with the twenty-seventh anniversary of the October Revolution in Cairo, in the town of Genefi. With this, the writer delicately confronts his relationship with the capabilities of the Soviet state.

The writer concludes the work with a desire to return to his homeland. In this memoir, which he wrote in 1958, he does not give information about his return to the motherland and his subsequent fate. The last sentence of the memory expresses two meanings: "Among the tears born of joy, I see my sad and painful days so clearly that ..." (20, p. 212). At first glance, the sentence evokes the reader's impression of the memory of the sufferings of the past days. But it hints that they could not write it for various reasons. As in the work of other autobiographical authors, Suleyman Valiyev "were under the pressure of the Soviet censorship, so the explanation of many topics was left unfinished" (2, p. 3).

The subsequent life of Suleyman Valiyev, whose arrival in literature coincided with the "bloody 30s", was not peaceful either. Although it was not his fault that he suffered the fate of captivity, the Stalinist regime did not forgive him. "In the biography of a

Soviet citizen, the fact of being in German captivity was an indelible stain that raised suspicions of treason and espionage for him" (27). After the end of the war, the writer, who returned to his homeland after a thousand hardships, was investigated and interrogated for a long time regarding his fate as a prisoner of war. Later, the true nature of this investigation becomes clear to the writer. Suleyman Valiyev is "offered" to participate in a secret plan organised against Samad Vurgun, a great poet who has supported him from time to time. Otherwise, Suleyman Valiyev would be released from his job in the Union of Writers and exiled to distant Siberia. A writer who categorically rejects this offer faces the expected consequences. The publication of the novel "Controversial City", delayed for eight years, was stopped, and the newly married writer was exiled to Siberia.

In his novel "Knots", Suleyman Valiyev reflected on the blows inflicted on human psychology by the unjust exile and the moral pain caused by the fate of the hero named Vasif. This work was a memorial to thousands of our unjustly destroyed compatriots" (9, p. 28). Vasif, the protagonist of the work, is the author's prototype. This is evidenced by the fact that the story of his life is similar to the life of the author "I was not lucky from the beginning, I had just started intelligence work in Girovdag when the war started, and I went to the army. I was confused and captured in the fighting in Sevastopol. Fate took me far away. Germany, Italy ... I escaped from the camp and joined the Italian partisans. At the end of the war, we came to Africa. I returned to my homeland in the forty-fifth year. I could not see my father. I worked in Girovdag. After three years, I was separated from my native land. Now I am returning to my homeland again. This time, too, my mother could not wait for me ... In a word, I could neither see my parents until I was satisfied, nor could I make them happy until I was satisfied" (22, p. 11). In work, the writer also describes in a highly effective way Vasif's feelings when he was taken prisoner after being shot in the head, his activities in the partisan movement, his life in exile, and the death of his parents without enduring the pain, finding the location of their graves after returning from exile, and learning that other people live in their homes. In their work, Suleyman Valiyev exposes the inner face of the regime because none of his relatives or acquaintances responded to his letters when he faced the fate of exile. His new acquaintance, Pakiza, who consoled him, said implicitly: "You know, the situation was different than" and allows us to guess the picture of the period. However, in the work's plot, the writer does not connect the reason for sending Vasif to exile with the fate of captivity, like the author himself, with the plan related to Samad Vurgun. In the novel, Vasif is slandered by his relative and sent into exile. With this, "by attributing the initial motive of the punishment to his relative, the writer made a certain compromise" (9, p. 28).

When Suleyman Valiyev wrote his thoughts about this novel even after some time, he does not openly admit that his hero is his prototype: "At first, in Girovdag, I became friends with the manager of the mine, the late Aliagha Aliyev, and the field chief, engineer Anvar Hasanov... I witnessed many events in Girovdag. Along with noble people and labour heroes, I also met lazy, slanderous, unsigned letter writers. Unfortunately, we

still meet such people. The events and conflicts in the novel "Knots" are a somewhat changed form of the events in Girovdag. There is a closeness between the fate of Vasif, the protagonist of the work, and the fate of Anvar Hasanov, whom I mentioned above" (20, p. 10-11). Both the change in the plot of the work and the "change" in the fact of its writing shows that the regime has softened, not changed in its whole meaning. "This caution of the writer was also because even though the repressed were acquitted, they were not allowed to write about it; the principles of socialist realism were followed. In the literary process of Azerbaijan, the realities of repression began to be written only in the 80s; almost all taboos on the topic of repression were removed" (3, p. 109).

Suleyman Valiyev wrote the absolute truth about the novel "Knots" only in the years of independence: "Most of my works are autobiographical. However, their heroes are generalised characters... My novel "Knots", which tells about the bitter fate of a warrior who was a victim of the cult of personality, was published in Azerbaijani, Russian and other languages but did not see life on the blue screen. They did not allow him to be filmed" (26, p. 29).

In his novel "Stone Spring", Suleyman Valiyev talks extensively about the people he met in Siberia, where he was sent into exile, and who helped him. However, taking into account the requirements of the time, the truths of repression were not reflected in this work. Even in the novel, the hero named Ayaz, the prototype of the author, is presented not as a citizen who came to Siberia as an exile but as an experimenter who came to conduct new experiments in agriculture. The writer describes the events he experienced by distorting the concepts of time and space. In the notes he wrote during the years of independence, issues related to the "activity" of the regime's censorship regarding the fate of this work are revealed: "My autobiographical novel "Stone Spring", which tells about my days in Siberia, was also damaged by the era of personality worship. Several necessary parts belonging to that period were reduced" (26, p. 29).

In the memoir "How I Resurrected", the writer turned the incident of receiving the card issued to war veterans into the subject of artistic thought. In the narrative, he relives his memories of the war. The writer, who had to submit documents related to his participation in the fight to receive a special privileges card, criticises the bureaucratic obstacles associated with this issue. However, the writer's more critical aspect is the issue of the regime selling these cards "in a second way". The writer achieves his goal with the sentence spoken by his acquaintance: "Dear son, everything can be solved quickly and easily with an acquaintance" (21, p. 232).

Suleyman Valiyev wrote several works on the subject of acts of repression, one of the bloodiest crimes of the Soviet regime. One of them is the essay "Chamanzaminli". In his documentary essay "Chamanzaminli", written in 1984, Suleyman Valiyev briefly discusses the fate of Y.V. Chamanzaminli, his teacher: "The time has come. Chamanzaminli, who always came to the training on time, was late for some reason. People waited for him for half an hour, but he didn't come, we thought he must be sick. The meeting did not take place. Then, later, we found out that

Chamanzaminli was called somewhere, but he could not go there. It didn't depend on him... Justice triumphs sooner or later, they say. After a long time, we met again with Chamanzaminli. But with his works". (24, p. 275)

Another memoir-story in which the writer wrote down his memories of the thirties is "Shushabandli (glasses gallery) Azernashr". In simple language, he conveys the terrible impressions of those years: "In 1937-38, black clouds covered the glass-enclosed, lighted Azernashr, just like everywhere else. Every morning we heard that someone was taken away in a black car. After the director of the publishing house, Ahmet Trinc, Asad Akhundov, Zulfugar Ahmadzadeh, and Baba Mammadov were branded "enemies of the people". One person (I have forgotten his name) was arrested here because he said during the conversation: "Stalin can also make mistakes..." Scary days began, and people spoke to each other cautiously. They said that even the wall has ears!" (26, p. 31)

In many of his works, Suleyman Valiyev tries to convey his thoughts against the Soviet regime in a coded form. An example is the expression "fate", which the writer often uses. If we take the word "fate" as the equivalent of the word "regime" in the writer's sentences, such as "Fate took me far away" and "Fate has a strange rule", it becomes clear what points the writer is alluding to. Suleyman Valiyev presents the flawed aspects of the regime, sometimes hiding them in the faces of the opposing heroes of his works and sometimes in the essence of the events. From this point of view, his story "Morning of Kerch" attracts attention. The writer values the tenacity, fearlessness, and bravery of the Soviet fighters as a factor determining the victory of the Soviet country. He exposes the regime's mistakes in the episodes of the events he presents: "When the enemies took Kerch for the second time in May 1942, the Soviet fighters stayed in the quarry for half a year and dealt significant blows to the fascists. The Hitlerites built barriers and mines all over the place, and finally, seeing that the Soviets did not surrender, they released gas there.

Thousands of our warriors died heroically in the cave. Mostly Azerbaijanis, Armenians, and Georgians. As if Transcaucasia had moved here. My daughter, this was the most horrible place. According to what I heard, several thousand people perished in one night ... Some of the wounded were given a spoonful of water and twenty-five grams of bread daily. The Hitlerites expected the people subjected to torture would eventually surrender and raise the white flag. They, on the contrary, raised a red flag in their dying days" (25, p. 186).

In these sentences, which at first glance seem to be written only about the strength of warriors, the writer points to a more critical point. The issue of the state's military power, which could not find out about the fate of thousands of its fighters for half a year, and was directly responsible for their transformation into victims, is touched upon, which can be considered a new stage for Suleyman Valiyev's creativity.

The writer continues this theme later in his memoir, "The bird with a broken wing has flown." In this work, the writer "tells the reader" in detail about his life from childhood until 1989, when he wrote the work. It highlights the sending of unarmed older adults to war,

the lack of tanks and military planes, the fact that most military units are unprepared for combat, and other issues. The head of state describes the accurate scale of Stalin's and army commander Mekhlis's mistakes and the magnitude of the tragedy as a result: "In May 1942, the situation on the Kerch front was even more terrible. The military command forbade digging trenches to overcome the fighters' desire to attack. This caused a significant loss in our army.

The high military command (Mehlis and others) made great strategic mistakes and fled by plane, leaving the army in danger and encirclement. It was a great betrayal. Due to their fault, many military units, especially Transcaucasian national divisions, were disabled. Tens of thousands of Soviet fighters sacrificed their lives here. The great "captive army" tragedy also began in this land. At that time, there was such a situation that there was no need for the prisoners to raise their hands to surrender. At that time, we said: "We were not captured." They captured us" (23. p. 60)

"Why didn't you kill yourself?" the investigator repeatedly asked. Süleyman Valiyev, faced with this question for the first time in this work, also reveals the real reason for the repression. The fundamental nature of the events is voiced by the investigator who interrogated him because he returned alive from the war: "Go to Samad Vurgu's house. Tell him about your hard life. He has a kind heart; he will help you ... Read your new works to him, make him warm to you... In between conversations, you will hear that he talks about the nation, defends the Pan-Turkists, and then... We need your words very much" (23, pp. 57-58).

Later, Süleyman Valiyev vividly describes the accurate picture of the time with the scene of his exile: "I knew from 1937 that people who were blacklisted were taken away from home in a closed black car at night. I was also waiting for my "night". But it happened the other way around. At noon, a militia officer knocked on my door and entered..." (23, p. 67)

In his autobiographical work "A bird with a broken wing has flown", the author emotionally expresses his difficulties in Siberia, his struggle for life, the fact that the investigations did not let him go, and the moral suffering caused by the regime's "stigmas": "Whoever has the number "-73" written on his card, he was considered a suspicious and fearful person. After serving his sentence, he was forbidden to live in 73 cities... It was clear then that I would not see Baku, the capital of the Azerbaijan Socialist Republic. I could not imagine such a cruel number being written on my paper. My hair was shivering when I thought about it" (23. p. 82).

At the end of the work, the author also mentions the trial of M.C. Bagirov, his complete acquittal, and Samad Vurgu's attitude to all these events. Even if the work was published in 1989, Süleyman Valiyev did not give complete freedom to his pen in this work either. Only after the independence of Azerbaijan, the writer manages to describe the true face of the Soviet regime and convey his hatred and the reasons for his hostility to the reader. The writer does not forget to get to the reader the reason why he did not write down all these facts in detail until today: "Stalin's oppression, the fear of repression was transmitted from our ancestors to our

blood, it did not leave our souls" (26, p. 4). The writer describes the regime's brutality more openly in his memoirs from the "Unopened Pages" series: "Stalin mercilessly oppressed the nations belonging to the Muslim religion during the Great Patriotic War and sowed the seeds of ruling nationalist chauvinism ... He treated innocent prisoners, especially Azerbaijanis, more severely and punished them mercilessly. The sufferings of our compatriots in the death camps are not enough; as they say, "the calamity of the imam" brought upon them" (26. p. 4).

For the first time, Süleyman Valiyev gave free rein to his pen in that memoir and tried to convey to the reader the terrible truths that he could not write during the Soviet era. He touched upon the issues related to the personality, whose name was forbidden by the regime. He decided to "talk" about the part of his life that he hid from everyone: "Fascists used to be about two thousand. They killed an Azerbaijani prisoner as a Jew because he was circumcised. Rasulzade, who heard about this matter, came to help and got into our blood. The brutality has ended. The fascists thought that the legionnaires would help them. They were wrong; the legion only saved Azerbaijanis from starvation and death. Muhammad Amin could not find a language not only with Stalin but also with Hitler. He disagreed that if the fascists won, Baku would submit to Berlin. That's why Hitler didn't allow him to live in Germany ... Muhammad Amin preferred the independence of our people - not subjugation to Moscow and Berlin above all else.

The legionnaires knew they would be punished more severely when they returned home, like a soldier serving in an enemy army. Therefore, they decided to hide their presence in the legion during interrogation" (26, p. 6).

After Stalin's death, in 1956, after being acquitted and returning to his homeland with his family, the writer did not leave literature at any time of his life; he wrote and created until the end of his life. Many works of the writer, who wrote a large number of stories, narratives, essays and novels, attract attention due to their autobiographical nature. By combining the facts of his life with the writer's imagination, Süleyman Valiyev succeeded in fictionalising the social conditions, spiritual sufferings, and pains of the people he could not express. No matter how cruel and merciless the regime's attitude was, Süleyman Valiyev managed not to remain silent but to turn the truths of life into the subject of artistic thought in a somewhat altered form. Süleyman Valiyev was focused on developing the educative direction of literature by creating a positive hero in the works he wrote by the requirements of socialist realism and observing the principle of non-conflict. In stories like "Illness", "Alas for those eyes", "Dyer", and so on, the writer turns people who are suffering from "duty disease" into targets of criticism. These people are promoted due to acquaintance, and showing that it is possible to step up the educational levels in different ways makes such people the target of criticism. It exposes the flawed aspects of the regime.

In the stories "Light", "The Brave of the Field", "Half-Millionaire", and the narrative "At the foot of the mountains", written by the writer, the "literary fashion" of the time described the socialist society, the labour process, and the simple problems of the people "As a

result, in Suleyman Valiyev's work, a unique concept of a militant man was formed, the struggle between man and time, his constant striving for the future, and his struggle for self-affirmation and freedom were embodied" (19, p. 25)

It would not be right to consider this step of the writer, who writes most of his works in the autobiographical genre, only as a "symbolic presentation of his emotional state" (13, p. 9). When the writer takes this step, he approaches the issue from a broader perspective. Although Suleyman Valiyev wrote his fate symbolically in his works, he succeeded in articulating the future of his people in that period. Analysing his works, it is possible to perceive not only the artistic description of the period but also the severity or lukewarmness of the censorship of literature. As noted by Professor Yashar Garayev, "... those who wrote and created in the Soviet era followed the code of "socialist realism", but they were not blind and mute performers of the official dictate from above, the "public order". In any case, the artistic heritage they left together gives a complete, clear and precise answer to the question "how did the prose of that time imagine and describe that time?" (15. p. 272).

Conclusion: In the works of Suleyman Valiyev, who came to literature in the most ambiguous years of our history, many events reflect the realities of the time. A large part of these realities is related to the circumstances faced by the writer himself. In these descriptions, it is possible to learn an accurate picture of the life and times of Suleyman Valiyev, who was a victim of the cruel and unjust decisions of the regime. It is clear from this that S. Valiyev could survive at the cost of great difficulties, but he did not remain silent but reflected the epochal truths of the time in his works as much as censorship allowed.

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